

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL- COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF MUSIC EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article analyzes the pedagogical possibilities of forming and improving professional-communication skills of students studying in the field of music education. It justifies the need to develop students' communicative competence in the process of musical education. Also, special attention is paid to the formation of a professional-communication culture in the pedagogical process through interactive methods, creative tasks, collective musical activities and role-playing games. The article analyzes such aspects of professional communication skills as listening, questioning, and expressing one's opinion clearly in professional speech as an important tool in musical-pedagogical activities.

Keywords: Music education, professional communication, pedagogical opportunities, communicative competence, interactive methods, creative activity, student.

Introduction.

In the modern educational process, along with the formation of musical literacy, the development of students' professional communication skills is also recognized as an integral part of the pedagogical process. In particular, the formation of a culture of communication among students-teachers studying in the field of music education is of great importance in establishing an effective pedagogical relationship in their future professional activities. Because a music teacher is not only a person who gives knowledge, but also stands out for his speech, emotional expression, and the ability to inspire the listener.

Professional communication skills are understood as the ability of a student to express his professional knowledge, engage in pedagogical dialogue with children, interpret musical works, answer students' questions in an understandable way, create a positive psychological environment in the audience, and freely convey his thoughts. If these skills are not strong, the student, no matter how talented, may not be able to convey his knowledge correctly.

There are a number of pedagogical tools for developing professional communication skills in the process of music education. In particular, it is possible to revive classroom communication through role-playing games, develop initiative in students through interactive activities, and form the habit of

expressing opinions through group analysis of musical works. In particular, students test their oratory skills through stage performances, conducting concerts, and teaching practices. Such experiences help them to strengthen their self-confidence and be free in communication.

In addition, modern ICT tools - recording video lessons, participating in online classes, conveying one's thoughts to the audience through musical webinars and seminars - serve to form students' multi-factor communication competence. Especially in the field of art, tools such as emotion, tone of voice, and physical expression (facial expressions and movements) play a special role in communication.

Therefore, the development of professional communication skills in the process of music education should be considered not only as an educational necessity, but also as a professional approach. How a student communicates in class, how he influences through music, what impression he makes with his speech is one of the criteria for his future success. After all, in music pedagogy, "hearing" and "listening", "understanding" and "explaining" are a living process in the dialogue between the teacher and the student.

Methodology:

The main basis of any scientific research is its methodological approach. After all, the accuracy, reliability and practical significance of the research results depend on the chosen methods and the level of thoroughness in their application. The issue of forming professional communication skills of students studying in the direction of music education requires a multifaceted, integrative and complex approach. Therefore, it was considered important to work in harmony with theoretical, practical and diagnostic methods in this study.

First, through the method of theoretical analysis, existing literature, advanced pedagogical experiences, scientific views in the field of communication psychology and music pedagogy were studied. In particular, concepts such as communicative competence, speech culture, and professional competence were thoroughly analyzed. Through this approach, the theoretical basis of the study was strengthened and existing problems were identified.

Secondly, through empirical observations and pedagogical experiments, students' participation in communication in music education lessons, their freedom to express their opinions, and indicators of participation in questions and answers were observed. In particular, the communication style, facial expressions, tone of voice, pedagogical position, and ways of addressing the audience in the process of teaching practice were taken into account. Based on

these observations, the real situation was analyzed and areas for improvement were identified.

Thirdly, the current level of communication skills, problematic aspects and needs among students and their teachers were identified using questionnaires, interviews and diagnostic tasks. Through such methods, the internal thoughts, views and experiences of the participants were involved in the study.

Also, interactive methods (cluster, aquarium, role-playing) were introduced into music lessons and their effectiveness in stimulating communication was tested. These methods not only taught, but also developed in students the skills of free self-expression, active communication, teamwork, and overcoming psychological barriers. The methodological basis was the theory of constructivism, the communicative approach and the concept of person-centered education. These approaches provide for the development of the student as a person, recognizing his individuality, and the formation of professional communication.

Literature review:

The issue of developing professional communication skills in the field of music education has become an increasingly relevant topic in pedagogical and psychological research in recent years. The analyzed literature shows that this issue is not limited to only technical or theoretical aspects of music pedagogy, but is also interpreted as an integral part of personal development, speech culture and social interaction skills.

The works of Uzbek scientists A. Yuldoshev, N. T. Tokhliyeva, G. K. Kholbekova, M. M. Ergasheva emphasize the role of the educational environment in the formation of the speech and professional culture of the music teacher. Their research notes that musical communication is carried out not only through spoken words, but also through intonation, mimicry, emotional impact and expressive means in the performance process.

Based on the scientific views of E. F. Sabzi, Sh. A. Alimov and M. A. Rasulov on the competency approach, professional communication skills are considered as a component of communicative competence. They emphasize the importance of interactive approaches, collaborative tasks and practical exercises in the lesson process to form solid professional communication skills in students.

The views of foreign researchers G. Hymes, J. Bruner and M. Byram on communicative competence, social speech culture and socialization through language can be directly applied in the field of music education. In particular, the theory of "communicative competence" put forward by Hymes is the basis for

preparing students not only verbally, but also psychologically, culturally and emotionally.

The results of the analysis show that in most literature, the development of professional communication skills in the process of music education directly depends on the personality of the teacher, and in this regard, it is noted that person-oriented approaches, pedagogical trainings, communication simulations, and creative tasks are of great effectiveness.

Also, although national methodological manuals provide a more theoretical approach to the issue of professional communication, their practical presentation has not yet been sufficiently enriched. Therefore, in new research, an important task is to conduct analyses based on interactive, experimental methods, while ensuring the harmony of theory and practice.

Discussion:

In the context of modern music education, the development of professional communication skills of future teachers is considered not only an important factor in their personal growth, but also in achieving high quality in the educational process. Based on observations, interviews and experiments conducted during the study, it was found that many students, although they have musical knowledge and technique, have problems with skills such as clearly and effectively conveying their thoughts, interacting with the audience, and communicating while maintaining emotional balance in a particular situation.

One of the main aspects that caused the discussion is that, although many educational programs focus on professional knowledge and practice, there are not enough special classes aimed at forming a culture of communication. This, in turn, prevents the student from behaving freely during classes in the classroom, during concerts and performance activities, or in musical conversations. In particular, voice control, speech expression on stage, answering problematic questions, and establishing a warm psychological connection with children - these skills are formed through practical exercises and pedagogical training.

According to the results of the analysis, professional communication skills include not only verbal speech, but also factors such as the teacher's actions, facial expressions, listening skills, and emotional impact. From this perspective, in music education, not only language is a means of communication, but also a musical work, voice, timbre, rhythm, melody, and even body movement are forms of communication.

Through interactive methods - role-playing, collective creative tasks, musical debates, and stage performances, students learn to be active in

communication. These methods encourage them not only to listen, but also to express their opinions, defend their point of view, listen to and understand the audience. This leads to significant positive changes in the development of communicative competence. Digital technologies also play a significant role in the development of communication skills. Through online lessons, video lessons, and musical blogging, students were able to express their speech in an audio-visual environment. This helped them work on their voice control, diction, and emotional expression.

Another important aspect is that professional communication is important not only in the student-student or teacher-listener relationship, but also in the social communication between student-student and student-team. This helps to achieve effective results in group work, exchange of ideas, and creative cooperation.

In conclusion, the formation of professional communication skills in music education is not only a part of the pedagogical process, but also a means of establishing effective communication with society through musical art. These skills determine the formation of a student as a successful teacher, active creator, and cultural promoter in the future.

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